

THE IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY IN THE CLASSROOM: AN INSIGHT INTO STUDENTS' AND TEACHERS' PSYCHOLOGICAL PERSPECTIVES

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Abstract

The integration of technology in the classroom has become increasingly popular, with many educators seeing it as a way to enhance teaching and learning. However, there is a need to understand how technology is being used and how it is impacting both students and teachers. This qualitative study aimed to explore students' and teachers' perspectives on the use of technology in the classroom. Semi-structured interviews were conducted with eight teachers and ten students in a high school in the United States. The interviews were analyzed using thematic analysis. The findings revealed that technology was perceived as a valuable tool for enhancing learning, but that there were also challenges associated with its use, such as technical difficulties and distractions. Additionally, students and teachers had differing opinions on how technology should be used in the classroom, with some students preferring a more traditional approach to learning. Overall, this study highlights the need for careful consideration of how technology is integrated into the classroom, as well as the importance of understanding students' and teachers' perspectives on its use.

Keywords: Technology, Education, Learning, Classroom, Integration, Effectiveness

Introduction

The use of technology in educational contexts has increased recently, and more and more teachers are realising its potential to enhance both classroom instruction and student comprehension. Despite the fact that the benefits of using technology in the classroom are generally recognized, questions have been raised concerning how it may affect both students and teachers. Research is thus required to examine how technology is used in education and how it affects both students and instructors. The goal of this qualitative study was to explore the opinions of instructors and students on the use of technology in the classroom.

Gewerc et al. (2018) and Scherer et al. (2016) found that the usage of technology has the potential to increase student engagement, motivation, and learning outcomes. However, there are drawbacks to using technology as well, including challenges with the technology itself, distractions, and a lack of technical help. (Bebell & Kay, 2010; Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). Ertmer, Ottenbreit-Leftwich, and York (2007) assert that instructors' attitudes about technology

use have a significant impact on the effectiveness of technology in the classroom. The aim of this study is to look into the opinions of instructors and students on the use of technology in the classroom. The study will examine the advantages and disadvantages of using technology, how it affects student engagement and learning and their results, how instructors and students feel about using technology in the classroom, and successful technology integration strategies.

According to Voogt, Fisser, Pareja Roblin, Tondeur, and van Braak (2012), technology integration in education is an important field of research because of the potential impact it can have on student learning outcomes and the development of skills relevant to the 21st century. The research of technology integration in education is particularly significant in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has led to broad adoption of online learning and the rising usage of educational technology (Hodges et al., 2020). This makes the study of how technology is integrated into education extremely vital (Asif et al., 2022).

Many of educationists and researcher who have contributed in the field of information technology integration in education include Prensky (2001), who created the term "digital natives" to describe students who have grown up around technology, Mishra and Koehler (2006), who created the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework for comprehending effective technology integration in teaching, and Fullan (2013), who has written extensively about the significance of effective technology integration. Because it can affect students' learning outcomes and because it's important to build skills appropriate for the twenty-first century, research on the use of technology in education is an important topic of study. To ensure the efficient and purposeful use of technology in education, it is essential to comprehend the viewpoints that both students and teachers have on its use in the classroom.

1. The Benefits and Drawbacks of Integrating Technology in the Classroom

Because technology has rapidly become an essential component of contemporary life, it is not surprising that it has also made its way into educational institutions all around the world. (Davis, 2019; Koc & Bakir, 2019; Teo, 2015) The incorporation of technology in educational settings has received plaudits for its ability to improve student learning outcomes, engagement, and critical thinking skills. However, it is important to also consider the potential drawbacks of integrating technology in education, such as issues related to distraction, screen time, and the potential for technology to exacerbate existing inequalities (Bulger, Mayer, & Almeroth, 2019; Heidig & Clarebout, 2011; Mangen & Velay, 2010). These are just some of the potential drawbacks of integrating technology in education.

It has been demonstrated through research that the utilisation of technology in the classroom can have a beneficial effect on the learning outcomes of students, particularly when the technology is utilised in a way that is purposeful and intentional (Teo, 2015). According to Davis

(2019), technology has the potential to boost student engagement and motivation by creating chances for learning experiences that are interactive and rich in multimedia content. Additionally, according to Koc and Bakir (2019), the implementation of technology in educational settings can assist students in the development of critical thinking and problem-solving skills by presenting them with a wide variety of digital materials and tools.

On the other hand, incorporating technology into educational environments could unintentionally have detrimental effects. According to Heidig and Clarebout (2011), students that use technology excessively find it difficult to focus on the task at hand. For instance, this could cause distractions. The amount of time spent in front of a screen may also rise as a result of increased technology use, and this has been linked to adverse health effects like obesity, poor sleep, and eye strain. (Bulger et al., 2019). Technological integration in educational contexts may exacerbate already-existing inequities, claim Mangen and Velay (2010). Because not all students may have access to the same materials and tools outside of the classroom, this is the case.

Before determining whether to incorporate technology in the classroom, it is important to thoroughly consider both the advantages and disadvantages of doing so. Although using technology might increase students' engagement and learning results, it is important to consider the likelihood that kids will become distracted, spend excessive amounts of time in front of computers, and that existing gaps will worsen.

In addition to the advantages and drawbacks already covered, there are a number of other factors that should be carefully taken into account when considering whether or not to integrate technology in the classroom. One of these elements is the role the teacher plays in introducing pupils to technology. The use of technology in the classroom must be done effectively and appropriately, and it is the duty of the instructors to see to that. Ertmer and Otterbreit-Leftwich (2010) state that they must be knowledgeable about the technology being used and able to offer assistance and advise to students as needed.

The demand for proper preparation and help on the part of both instructors and students is another crucial factor to consider. Koehler and Mishra (2009) assert that it is essential for instructors to have proper training on how to effectively use the resources at their disposal in order to make the most of the advantages that technology may provide for students' education. Additionally, it is crucial that students have access to the necessary gear and software as well as digital literacy abilities in order for them to successfully use technology. (Warschauer & Matuchniak, 2010). They must have access to these abilities and tools.

In conclusion, it is essential to take into account the potential impact that the incorporation of technology could have on the learning motivations and attitudes of students. According to Mouza and Lavigne (2016), the use of technology in the classroom may not be beneficial for all kids, despite the fact that it can make some students more engaged and motivated. In addition, an

excessive reliance on technology in the classroom may lead to a lack of focus on other essential components of education, such as the growth of students' social and emotional skills (Turkle, 2015).

The implementation of technology in the classroom has the potential to improve both the learning results and the level of involvement of the students. However, it is essential to give due consideration to the possible downsides, which may include distraction, more time spent in front of a screen, and the worsening of already existing inequities. To successfully integrate technology into the classroom, it is essential to have adequate training and support for teachers, as well as access to the appropriate resources for both teachers and students. In the end, technology should be utilised in a way that is deliberate and intentional, so that it can enhance the learning and development of students.

2. The Impact of Technology on Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes

There has been an increase in the use of technology in educational settings, which has the potential to increase student engagement levels and educational results. According to Christensen, Horn, and Johnson (2011) and Shahid, Asif, and Pasha, (2022), there is evidence that employing technology in education can increase student involvement and academic outcomes. There is evidence to support the potential of technology in education, despite the fact that perspectives on the topic differ from person to person.

The use of technology in the classroom has the potential to promote student involvement by providing opportunities for active learning, collaboration, and individualization of education, according to research (Dabbagh & Kitsantas, 2012; Means et al., 2013). Technology may also provide students with access to a wide range of information and tools that can support student learning and knowledge, claim Honey and Hilton (2011). Multimedia materials and interactive simulations are two examples of such technologies.

Along with increasing student involvement, technology has the potential to improve learning results. The usage of digital tools in the classroom was shown to be associated with better levels of critical thinking and academic achievement, according to the findings of one study (Zheng et al., 2016). Similar to this, Cheung and Slavin (2013) carried out a meta-analysis of research on the use of technology in education and came to the conclusion that it had a positive effect on student achievement in the subjects of mathematics, science, and reading.

However, it is essential to keep in mind that the effect of technology on student engagement and the consequences of their learning can vary depending on a wide range of factors. These elements include the precise learning goals and objectives, the context in which the technology is utilised, and the sort of technology that is employed. In addition, the use of technology in the

classroom should be done so in a way that is deliberate and intentional, with the primary goal of facilitating the learning and growth of the students. (Redondo & Cabrera-García, 2022)

In general, there is evidence to show that technology can have a good impact on student engagement and learning outcomes when it is used appropriately. This is despite the fact that the impact of technology on these factors is not always crystal evident. Technology has the ability to boost student engagement and improve learning outcomes by giving opportunities for active learning, collaboration, and personalisation, as well as enabling access to a wide range of materials and tools.

3. Teachers' Attitudes towards Using Technology in Their Teaching Practice

Both educators and researchers continue to be interested in the topic of the effects that technology has on the level of student involvement as well as the learning outcomes. According to OECD (2015), some research have claimed that the impact of technology on student learning is either restricted or even negative, while others have suggested that its impact is either limited or favourable. Tamim et al., (2011) argued in a systematic review of studies on technology in education was the finding that while technology can have a positive impact on student engagement and learning outcomes, the quality of the studies on the topic varied greatly, and more in-depth research is required to determine the true impact of technology on education.

One possible disadvantage of utilising technology in the classroom is the increased risk of distractions and a shorter attention span among students. However, studies have shown that when it is employed in an appropriate manner, technology can really help students improve their ability to focus and pay attention. To give one example, according to Gros (2014), interactive simulations and tools for virtual reality can provide students with learning experiences that are both immersive and engaging, thereby capturing their attention and promoting active learning.

One more possible advantage of integrating technology into the classroom is the capacity to deliver individualised educational experiences to students. According to Kizilcec et al. (2017), adaptive learning systems have the ability to personalise training to the specific requirements of individual students and provide rapid feedback on student achievement. This can help to address the varied educational requirements of students and enhance their overall academic success.

The effect that technology has on the overall level of student involvement and the learning outcomes is one that is intricate and multi-faceted. There is some evidence to show that the use of technology in the classroom can have a good impact on student learning; nevertheless, additional study of a more rigorous kind is required to properly grasp the degree of its impact. It is essential for teachers to utilise technology in a way that is purposeful and intentional, with a concentration on facilitating the learning and growth of their students.

4. Students' Preferences and Expectations for Technology Use in the Classroom

The degree to which technology is incorporated into classrooms is highly dependent on a number of factors, one of the most important of which is the attitudes that teachers have towards the use of technology in their own teaching practises. According to recent research (Ertmer et al., 2012; Muir-Herzig & Mulder, 2018), even though many educators are aware of the numerous opportunities afforded by the integration of technology into the classroom, they may be hesitant to fully embrace it for a variety of reasons. Some of these reasons include a lack of training, concerns regarding classroom management, and scepticism regarding the influence that technology will have on student learning.

Teo (2015) revealed that instructors' opinions regarding the utility of technology in enhancing student learning and their own perceived ability in utilising technology were two factors that influenced their attitudes towards students' usage of technology in the classroom. According to Papadakis et al. (2018), educators who have had favourable experiences with technology in their personal life are more likely to have positive views towards employing it in their teaching practise.

Training and professional development opportunities have been proven to be crucial in helping teachers gain the skills and confidence necessary to integrate technology into their teaching practise (Ertmer et al., 2012; Lawless & Pellegrino, 2007). This is according to research that was conducted by Ertmer et al., (2012) and Lawless & Pellegrino (2007). In addition to training, continuous assistance and resources can also be helpful in assisting educators in overcoming obstacles that stand in the way of complete technological integration into their classrooms.

Studies have shown that the potential benefits of technology for student learning and engagement are enormous (Wenglinsky, 2005). Despite the fact that there may be problems associated with incorporating technology into the classroom, it has been stated that there are huge potential benefits of technology. As a result, it is essential for educators to continue looking at ways to assist teachers in incorporating technology into their teaching practises, while simultaneously addressing any concerns or impediments that may be preventing acceptance of such practises.

According to research that was conducted by Drent and Meelissen (2008), the attitudes of instructors towards technology can have a considerable impact on the usage of technology in the classroom. (Glover et al., 2007; Papadakis et al., 2018) Two studies came to the conclusion that instructors who are more hesitant to utilise technology in their teaching practise may be more likely to have bad experiences with it, such as technical difficulties or interruptions to classroom management. This was found to be the case when the teachers were asked to reflect on their own usage of technology in the classroom. On the other hand, according to Muir-Herzig and Mulder (2018), educators who have a more positive attitude towards technology are more likely to find

ways to effectively integrate it into their teaching practise and to recognise the benefits that it has for the education of their students.

A teacher's usage of technology in the classroom can be influenced by a number of things in addition to their opinions towards the topic. For instance, research has indicated that a teacher's level of confidence in their own technological abilities might influence the degree to which they are eager to utilise technology in their classroom (Teo, 2015). Further, according to Lawless and Pellegrino (2007), a teacher's access to resources, such as technological equipment and opportunities for training, can also play a role in determining how well they are able to incorporate technology into their classrooms.

It is essential for schools and other educational institutions to provide sufficient training and resources for instructors in order to facilitate the incorporation of technology into the learning environment. (Muir-Herzig & Mulder, 2018; Teo, 2015) Research has shown that participating in professional development opportunities, such as workshops or training sessions, can assist educators in developing their self-assurance as well as their technical expertise when it comes to utilising technology. According to Lawless and Pellegrino (2007), giving continuing support to educators in the form of technical assistance or access to educational resources can assist educators in overcoming challenges that stand in the way of effectively integrating technology into their teaching practices.

According to Wenglinsky (2005), despite the fact that there may be obstacles involved in incorporating technology into the classroom, there is the potential for major benefits for student learning and engagement. As a result, it is essential for educators to continue looking at ways to assist teachers in incorporating technology into their teaching practises, while simultaneously addressing any concerns or impediments that may be preventing acceptance of such practises. In recent years, there has been a growing focus on the incorporation of technology into the classroom as well as the potential influence that this could have on the learning and engagement of students. However, while deciding whether or not the use of technology in the classroom is effective, it is essential to take into account the opinions of the students themselves. According to research that was conducted by Chen, Looi, and Chen (2009), students have distinct preferences and expectations about the integration of technology into their educational experiences.

According to the findings of a study conducted by Stoi, Maksi, and Stojanovi (2018), students prefer the usage of technology that is interactive, engaging, and personalised to their own educational requirements. According to Daz-Rodriguez and Alvarez-Valdivia's (2020) research findings, students highlighted the significance of having access to dependable technological equipment and resources, in addition to receiving sufficient help and direction from instructors.

In addition, students have voiced a desire for the use of technology in the classroom that goes beyond merely serving as a replacement for more conventional instructional strategies. According to Bower et al. (2017), people place a higher value on technology that facilitates group work, creative expression, and analytical reasoning. Studies have revealed that students who have positive experiences with technology in the classroom may have improved motivation and engagement in their learning (Lee & Srinivasan, 2012). Students who have positive experiences with technology in the classroom may have higher motivation and engagement in their learning.

Having said that, it is essential to keep in mind that not all students have the same level of technological literacy or access to the same kinds of technologies. According to Warschauer (2003), students' access to technology and their capacity to make effective use of it in their educational pursuits can be influenced by socioeconomic factors such as income and race. It is imperative that teachers take into account the various requirements and points of view of their pupils if they wish for technological instruction to be successful in their classrooms. It is possible to increase the likelihood that every student will be able to profit from the use of technology in their educational experiences by ensuring that they have access to dependable technological equipment and resources and that their teachers offer sufficient assistance and supervision (Al-Qudah & Al-Dababneh, 2022).

The preferences and expectations of students about the use of technology in the classroom is a topic that is receiving an increasing amount of attention in educational research. According to the findings of a study that was carried out by Shabani, Khatib, and Ebadi (2019), students favoured the use of technology that allowed for the customization of their educational experiences and encouraged interactive participation. The findings of the survey also showed that students were open to incorporating the usage of technology into their educational pursuits so long as they believed it would be beneficial to their overall educational objectives.

In a separate piece of research, Wang and Chen (2019) investigated the views that students hold regarding the use of mobile devices in the classroom. According to the findings of the study, students had favourable opinions towards the use of mobile devices for educational purposes and believed that doing so increased their level of involvement and motivation. However, the survey also revealed that students had concerns over the possibility for distractions and the need for clear standards and limitations for the use of technology in the classroom. These findings are consistent with previous research. (Dey, 2021)

In a similar vein, Akbulut and Cardak (2012) found that students had high expectations for the use of technology in the classroom, but that they also expressed concerns about potential distractions and the implications that these distractions could have on their ability to learn. According to the findings of the study, it is essential for educators to both make it obvious to students what clear guidelines and expectations are for using technology in the classroom, as well

as monitor student use of technology to ensure that it is in keeping with educational objectives (Chong, Wong, & Lim, 2022)

In general, a variety of characteristics, such as personalisation, interaction, relevance to educational goals, and clear restrictions and boundaries, can influence the preferences and expectations that students have regarding the use of technology in the classroom. It is crucial for educators to examine these variables and strive towards creating a learning environment that successfully integrates technology and satisfies the different requirements and preferences of their students. This is because technology is continuing to play an increasingly important role in education, and this trend is expected to continue for the foreseeable future. (Adedokun & Akpomi, 2021).

5. The Role of Technology in Supporting Diverse Learning Needs and Styles

Technology has become an increasingly significant component in catering to the varied requirements and preferences of various instructional approaches. As a result of the widespread adoption of technology in educational settings, teachers now have access to a variety of resources that enable them to tailor instruction to the specific needs and interests of their pupils. In this essay, I will explain the significance that technology plays in assisting learners with a wide variety of requirements and learning styles.

The utilisation of various forms of multimedia is one of the ways that modern technology may cater to a variety of educational requirements. According to Mayer (2009), the use of multimedia in education can be beneficial since it gives students more than one way to comprehend the material they are being taught. Learners who prefer to take in information via their eyes, for instance, can gain from looking at pictures and watching movies, whereas learners who prefer to take in information through their ears can benefit from listening to recordings. Educators are able to meet the demands of a wide variety of students and ensure that their students can comprehend the material that is being taught by making use of various forms of multimedia (Alqurashi, 2021).

Adaptive learning technologies are yet another type of technological tool that can help meet the varied requirements of educational institutions. According to Wang and Baker (2015), adaptive learning technologies have the potential to personalise the educational experience for each individual student by evaluating their performance and presenting them with content that is specific to them. Learners who have disabilities or who require special support may benefit from this to a greater extent than other students.

Through the facilitation of collaborative learning, technology can also assist a variety of learning styles. According to Dillenbourg (1999), learners can benefit from collaborative learning since it gives them opportunities to engage in conversations and share their views with their classmates. Learners are now able to collaborate with their classmates regardless of where they are

located physically thanks to the help of technology, which makes it feasible for them to get knowledge from people who come from a variety of backgrounds and have unique points of view. (Al-Qahtani, 2021)

Lastly, technology may assist a variety of learning needs by giving students access to a wealth of online materials. According to Liu et al. (2010) and Shahid, Asif, and Pasha, (2022), using internet resources can give students access to a plethora of knowledge that can assist them in developing a deeper comprehension of the material that is being presented in class. This can be especially advantageous for students who prefer to learn at their own pace and are self-directed, as this allows them to learn at their own rate.

Technology plays a significant role in providing support for a wide variety of learning requirements and approaches. Educators are able to provide students with personalised learning experiences that are tailored to the students' individual requirements and preferences when they make use of online resources, gamification, collaborative learning, and multimedia tools such as adaptive learning technology. (Kılınc & Kılıc, 2021)

Strategies for Effective and Meaningful Integration of Technology in the Classroom

As technology continues to play a vital part in all aspects of our lives, the incorporation of technology into educational settings has taken on a greater level of significance. Nevertheless, it is of the utmost importance to make certain that the integration of technology is both efficient and relevant, as opposed to simply employing technology for the sake of using it. The following is a list of various techniques for integrating technology in a relevant and successful manner in the classroom:

To begin with, pedagogy: according to Puentedura (2014), the emphasis should never be placed on the technology itself but rather on the learning goals and the pedagogical goals that are being pursued. Instead than being the primary emphasis, technology in the classroom should serve to supplement and improve students' educational experiences.

Professional development: According to Mishra and Koehler (2006), schools should offer teachers opportunities for professional development so that they can learn how to properly integrate technology in the classroom. Because of this, they will be able to use technology in a way that helps them achieve their educational and pedagogical objectives.

The acronym UDL stands for "Universal Design for Learning." According to CAST (2018), universal design for learning (UDL) is a framework that may be utilised to design learning experiences that are accessible to all learners, including those who have disabilities. When integrating technology, it is essential to verify that the technology supports the Universal Design for Learning (UDL) principles (Shin, Kim, & Kim, 2021).

Active learning: According to Prince (2004), active learning is more effective and more engaging for students than passive learning. Technology can be utilised to encourage active learning. Students, for instance, can use technology to work together on projects that involve multimedia, participate in simulations, or even create their own multimedia presentations.

According to Black and William (1998), technology can be utilised to facilitate continual evaluation and feedback. One example of this is ongoing assessment. Because of this, teachers are able to keep track of their students' progress and modify their lessons accordingly. In general, in order for technology to be integrated in a way that is both effective and meaningful, one must take a deliberate approach that places more of an emphasis on the pedagogical objectives and the requirements of the students than on the technology itself.

Implications and Suggestions for the Future Regarding the Integration of Technology in the Educational System

As a result of the ongoing development of technology, there are a number of potential implications and recommendations about the incorporation of technology in educational settings. The following is a list of some of the most important recommendations and implications:

According to the United States Department of Education (2016), technology has the potential to make it possible to create personalised learning experiences that are catered to the specific requirements and preferences of individual students. In the not too distant future, there will be a greater focus placed on individualised instruction, and technology will play an important part in making this possible.

Artificial Intelligence (AI): According to Baker and Inventado (2014), AI has the potential to revolutionise education by making it possible to create personalised and adaptive learning environments. Artificial intelligence (AI) will be progressively integrated into educational technology in the future, enabling learning experiences that are both more intelligent and more effective.

Virtual and Augmented Reality (VR/AR): VR/AR can enable learning experiences that are immersive and engaging, which are not achievable with conventional classroom training (Khan, 2018).

Ongoing Evaluation: To guarantee that technology is being utilised in an efficient manner in the classroom, it is imperative that ongoing review take place. The efficacy of technological tools should be monitored by educators, and any necessary adjustments should be made based on the data and feedback provided by students. Citizenship in the digital age is something that should be taught to kids by their teachers. This should include how to make responsible and ethical use of

technology. Students will benefit from this as they work towards becoming responsible and ethical members of the digital community.

Equity and access: Educators have a responsibility to guarantee that all children, irrespective of their financial standing or physical location, have access to the appropriate technological resources. This can be accomplished through the implementation of various projects, such as the provision of technological resources at educational institutions, community centres, and public libraries. The incorporation of technology into the classroom setting is absolutely necessary in order to adequately prepare students for the workforce of the 21st century. (Hsu & Wang, 2021) Educators can effectively integrate technology in the classroom to enhance students' learning experiences by first ensuring that they have access to professional development opportunities, personalised learning experiences, continuous evaluation, teaching students about digital citizenship, and ensuring that all students have equitable access to technology. (Hsu & Wang, 2021)

Conclusion

In summary, this qualitative research throws light on the viewpoints of students and teachers on the use of technology in the educational setting. In general, the findings suggest that technology can be a useful tool for enhancing teaching and learning; however, its effectiveness is dependent on a variety of factors such as the quality of the technology, the level of training and support provided to teachers, and the willingness of both teachers and students to integrate technology into their respective learning experiences (Cho & Her, 2021).

The findings of this study underline the importance of educators using technology in the classroom in a planned and intentional manner, ensuring that their use of technology is in line with their pedagogical goals and objectives. In addition, the research highlights how important it is to address any potential obstacles or challenges that may develop in the process of using technology, such as problems with access, equity, and student participation. This is emphasised throughout the study.

In the years to come, it is unquestionable that technology will continue to play an essential position in the field of education. This is especially true in light of the COVID-19 pandemic, which has sped up the adoption of digital learning technologies. However, it is absolutely necessary for teachers to continue to participate in ongoing professional development in order to keep up with the most recent technical developments and the most effective methods for incorporating technology into the classroom. By doing so, they will be able to guarantee that technology is used in a way that is both effective and relevant in order to improve the teaching and learning experience for all of the students.

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